

Reporting checklist for protocol of a systematic review and meta analysis.

Based on the PRISMA-P guidelines.

		Reporting Item	Page Number
Title			
Identification	#1a	The study has been identified as a protocol for a systematic review.	1
Update	#1b	This is not an update of a previous review, so this item is not applicable.	n/a
Registration			
	#2	The review is registered with PROSPERO, registration number CRD42023452489.	1
Authors			
Contact	#3a	Authors, affiliations, and contact information are provided.	1
Contribution	#3b	Contributions of protocol authors are outlined; the guarantors of the review is Dr. Simone Ciaccioni, given the correspondence address.	1
Amendments			
	#4	If there are amendments to this protocol, plan to document important protocol amendments in future updates or correspondences.	n/a
Support			
Sources	#5a	Co-funded by the European Union	8
Sponsor	#5b	Not applicable.	n/a
Role of sponsor or funder	#5c	Not applicable.	n/a

Introduction

Rationale #6 The rationale for the review, including the importance of physical education in hospital schools, is well-described. 2-3

Objectives #7 The objective is clearly stated. 3

Methods

Eligibility criteria #8 Study characteristics, including PICO (participants, interventions, comparators, outcomes), study design, setting, time frame, and report characteristics, are specified. 3-5

Information sources #9 Intended information sources such as electronic databases are described. 5

Search strategy #10 A draft search strategy for at least one database, including planned limits to ensure reproducibility, is provided. 5,13

Study records - data management #11a Softwares and review platform are mentioned for managing records and data. 5

Study records - selection process #11b A two-phase screening process involving independent reviewers is outlined. 5

Study records - data collection process #11c The method for data extraction, including independent extraction and consensus, is described. 5,6

Data items #12 Variables for which data will be sought are listed, including PICO items and comparators. 4-5

Outcomes and prioritization #13 Outcomes for data collection are listed. 4

Risk of bias in individual studies #14 Methods for assessing the risk of bias, including tools like Rob 2.0 and ROBINS-I, are described. 6

Data synthesis #15a Our protocol mentions the intention to use meta-analytic techniques if the data from the included studies exhibit sufficient homogeneity. This indicates a criterion for quantitative synthesis—homogeneity among studies. 6-7

Data synthesis	#15b	For quantitative synthesis, meta-analysis using a random-effects model will be preferred.	6-7
Data synthesis	#15c	Additional analyses such as sensitivity or subgroup analyses are described.	6-7
Data synthesis	#15d	If quantitative synthesis is not appropriate due to high heterogeneity or insufficient data, we plan to synthesize findings narratively.	6-7
Meta-bias(es)	#16	Plans for assessing meta-bias, such as publication bias, are specified.	7
Confidence in cumulative evidence	#17	We will use the GRADE methodology to assess the quality of the evidence for each key outcome.	7

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